

CYANINE DYES FROM β -NAPHTHAQUINALDINE

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Four new cyanine dyes have been prepared by the condensation of β -naphthaquinaldine ethiodide with *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde, *p*-toluquinaldine ethiodide, 6-ethoxyquinaldine ethiodide and *p*-toluquinoline ethiodide, and their optical, photographic and other properties studied. The effect of the change of molecular weight, structure and substituents on the sensitising power of these and other related compounds has been discussed.

Cyanine dyes derived from β -naphthaquinaldine are known to be good sensitisers (Mills and Pope, *Phot. J.*, 1920, 60, 193; Mees and Gutekunst, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1922, 14, 1060; Hamer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 212; Hamar and Kelly, *ibid.*, 1931, 778; D. R. P. 158349). Recent work has shown (Leermakers, Carrol and Stand, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1937, 5, 378; Schwarz, *Sci. Ind. Phot.*, 1939, 10, 233; Levkoev and Natanson, *Acta Physicochem.*, 1946, 21, 437; Brooker and Eastman Kodak Co., U. S. P. 2461137/1949; Dickinson, *Phot. J.*, 1950, 90B, 142) that even minor structural changes, such as the replacement of one small group by another, considerably affects the aggregation of cyanine dyes, and consequently changes their sensitising power. Further impetus to the preparation of new types of dyes has been given by the observation that the sensitising efficiency of a cyanine dye is increased by an admixture with another dye, which may or may not possess a sensitising characteristic itself (Hamar, *Quart. Rev.*, 1950, 4, 353). This is known as "supersensitisation". It is an important advance, and a number of compounds have been claimed as supersensitisers (B.P. 518478, 518067; U. S. P. 2398778, 2380940). This has been of great help in the preparation of highly sensitive, special quality photographic emulsions (Kendal, *Phot. J.*, 1950, 90B, 165). In view of these considerations we have attempted to prepare a few new β -naphthaquinaldine-derived cyanine dyes.

Four compounds have been prepared and investigated. (A) has been obtained by the condensation of β -naphthaquinaldine ethiodide with *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde under the catalytic influence of piperidine. This belongs to the "Pinaflavol" type of cyanine dyestuff. (B), (C) and (D) have been obtained by the interaction of β -naphthaquinaldine ethiodide with *p*-toluquinaldine ethiodide, 6-ethoxyquinaldine ethiodide and *p*-toluquinoline ethiodide respectively, in the presence of alcoholic KOH. They are all cyanine dyes of the "isocyanine" type and differ from one another only in the nature of the substituents in the 2' and 6' positions of the quinoline nucleus. Whereas (B) has methyl groups in both these positions, (C) has one methyl and one ethoxyl group, and (D), only one methyl group in the 6' position.

[Note—According to the modern concept of the the structure of cyanine dyes, the positive charge of the cation is distributed over the two basic groups, the molecule being regarded as a resonance hybrid of two canonical structures. The formulae shown below therefore represent resonance extremes only].

β -Naphthaquinaldine ethiodide has been used by several workers in the synthesis of cyanine dyes, but nowhere we have been able to find its preparation details. We obtained β -naphthaquinaldine by the method of Döbner and von Miller (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 1711), and the base was quaternised by a prolonged water-bath heating in a sealed tube with a slight excess of ethyl iodide.

In regard to yield (A) gives the highest (72.8%). Among the isocyanines (D) is the best with a yield of 43.8%; (B) comes next with 28.28 and (C), last with 24.06%.

(A) being the lightest molecule it has the lowest melting point, 189°. Again of the three isocyanines, (D) has the lowest molecular weight and therefore perhaps possesses the lowest m.p. 218°. This, however, is not the rule. (C), although heavier than (B), has a lower m.p., 220° and 225° respectively. All the four compounds are readily soluble in methyl and ethyl alcohol and insoluble in ether. (B) is only slightly soluble in chloroform, but (C), (D) and (A) dissolve a little more. (A) is soluble in water and becomes more so on warming. The other three compounds dissolve less easily in this solvent.

Alcoholic solutions of these compounds are all coloured with a red-violet shade. Their relative intensities are given in column 6 of Table I. These have been colorimetrically determined for 1:50,000 solutions in rectified spirit. It will be noticed that the pinaflavol compound (A) is the most intensely coloured and the diethyl isocyanine (B), the least so.

Their solutions are decolorised by acids. It has been suggested that this process involves the addition of a proton to the methin chain and consequently the loss of resonance stabilisation, which is responsible for the colour (Maccoll, *Quart. Rev.*, 1947, 1, 50; Brooker *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1889). The relative resistance to decolorisation of these dyestuffs is given in column 5 of Table I. It will be seen that (A) is pronouncedly much more resistant than the other three compounds. (C) and (D) are almost equally resistant.

In columns 2, 3 and 4 respectively are recorded the colour and shape of the crystals of these compounds, their reflexes and the pleochroic characteristics exhibited by them.

The sensitisation spectra of the new dyes are given in Fig. 1, along with that of an unbathed plate for the purpose of comparison. Their salient features have been summarised in Table I, column 7.

The first compound (A) is a powerful photographic sensitiser. The sensitisation has been extended to $\lambda 7400$, and the maxima are located at $\lambda 5600$ and $\lambda 6600$. It is of interest to note in this connection that the corresponding dimethyl compound, that is to say the 2-*p*-dimethylaminostyryl- β -naphthaquincline ethiodide, sensitises only up to $\lambda 7000$ with a maximum at $\lambda 6200$ (Bloch and Hamer, *Phot. J.*, 1930, 70, 386). Thus by changing the alkyl radicals attached to the ternary nitrogen atom, from methyl to ethyl, there has been an augmentation of the sensitising power, which is more than that produced by the addition of a benzene ring (Hamer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 999). 2-*p*-Dimethylaminostyryl-acenaphthapyridine methiodide sensitises up to $\lambda 7100$ and has its maximum at $\lambda 5750$. However, it is not always that the replacement of methyl radicals by ethyl radicals in cyanine dyes produces an increased sensitisation. Thus, 1:1'-dimethyl-5:6-benz- ψ -cyanine iodide sensitises up to $\lambda 6300$ and has a maximum at $\lambda 5700$, whereas 1:1'-diethyl-5:6-benz- ψ -cyanine iodide sensitises only up to $\lambda 6100$, and has the maximum at $\lambda 5750$ (Hamer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 212).

In the compound (B) the sensitisation extension is up to $\lambda 6500$ and the maxima at $\lambda 5400$ and $\lambda 6000$. In (C) the sensitisation extends to $\lambda 6400$, and the maxima are at $\lambda 5500$ and $\lambda 5950$. Here there is also a faint sensitisation band at $\lambda 6800$. The sensitisation spectrum of (D) is very similar to that of (C) except that in this case the sensitivity at $\lambda 6803$ becomes well defined.

Fig. 1

(B) is a slightly better sensitiser than (C) which may mean that the replacement of a methyl group by an ethoxyl group in the 6' position has not been beneficial. Of the three, (D) has the most extensive sensitisation band, and it has no substituent in the 2' position. We therefore confirm the observation of Mills and Pope (*Phot. J.*, 1920, 60, 198) that in this class of dyes, from the point of view of sensitising efficiency, the loading of the 2' position is not advantageous.

Because of their close relationship, in each case the absorption spectrum of the dye is given below the sensitisation spectrum in Fig. 1. The frequencies of maximum absorption are recorded in column 8 of Table I.

The fluorescence of weak alcoholic solutions of these dyes is given in Table II (also see Jelly, *Nature*, 1936, 138, 1009).

TABLE I

Compound.	Colour and shape.	Reflex.	Pleochroism.		5. Rel. resist. to decolorisation.	6. Rel. intens. of colour in soln.	7. Extra sensitisation.		8. Frequency of maximum absorption
			Position one.	Position at right ang			Range	Maxima	
A	Very dark sage-green crystals	Scintillating bottle-green	Amethyst	Colorless	7.28	3.33	5000—7400Å	5600 & 6600Å	57250 × 10 ¹⁰
B	Greenish stunted needles	Greenish yellow	Colorless	Opaque	1.0	1.0	5100—6500	5400 & 6000	53090 × 10 ¹⁰
C	Dark green needles	Golden green	Light green	Brownish green	2.08	1.42	5200—6400 faint band at 6800Å	5500 & 5950	52170 × 10 ¹⁰
D	Dark felt-green crystals	Shining green	Grey	Yellowish green	1.92	1.60	5200—6550Å well defined band at 6800Å	5500 & 6000	53380 × 10 ¹⁰

TABLE II

Colour of the fluorescent beam seen at right angles to the incident beam.

Wallace colour filter No.	A.	B.	C.	D.
1	Light absorbed	Light absorbed	Light absorbed	Light absorbed
2	Orange	Orange-red	Red	Orange
3	Blue violet	Violet	Blue	Blue-violet
4	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange
5	Pink	Claret red	Red	Deep pink
6	Orange-yellow	Orange	Faint red	Faint orange*
7	Faint violet	Red-violet	Violet	Violet
8	Light violet	Violet	Faint yellowish blue	Deep violet
9	Blue-violet	Pink-violet	Blue	Deep violet
10	Faint yellow	Reddish orange	Pink	Faint violet

The colours imparted to silk, wool and cotton on dyeing with these compounds are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Compound.	Wool.	Silk.	Cotton.
A	Black	Deep red-violet	Black berry
B	Violet	Faint red-violet	Red-violet
C	Deep violet	Violet	Light violet
D	Deep chocolate	Light violet	Violet

(A) is a powerful photographic sensitiser. It was thought of interest to compare its properties with other similarly constituted cyanines. For this purpose six compounds in two sets, along with their formulae, important characteristics and other relevant information, have been collected in Table IV. They are arranged in order of decreasing molecular weight, this having been attained by knocking out a benzene ring as we descend the series. In the bottom set additional decrease in weight has been achieved by having two methyl radicals attached to the ternary nitrogen atom instead of ethyl.

It is known that increase in the size of a cyanine dye shifts its sensitisation spectrum farther towards the red. This is true of all the cyanines under consideration. In each set, the heavier dye sensitises farther into the red than the next lighter dye.

Mills and Pope (*Phot. J.*, 1920, 60, 256) observed that 1:1'-diethylcarbocyanine iodide is a much better sensitiser than the corresponding dimethyl compound, 1:1'-dimethylcarbocyanine iodide.

TABLE IV

Compound.	M.W.	Crystal shape.	M.p.	Absorption maximum.	Sensitisation		Reference.
					Range.	Maximum.	
2- <i>p</i> -Diethylamino-styryl- β -naphthoquinoline ethiodide	508	Sage-green crystals	189°	5240	3900 to 7400 Å	6600 Å	(A)
2- <i>p</i> -Diethylamino-styrylquinoline ethiodide	458	Light chocolate needles	230°	...	4200 to 6400 Å	5800	(i) Doja <i>et al.</i> , this <i>Journal</i> , 1943, 20, 153 (ii) Doja and Prasad, <i>Patna Univ. J.</i> , 1945, 2, No. 1, 6.
2- <i>p</i> -Diethylamino-styrylpyridine ethiodide	408	Vermillion-red needles	205°	...	4200 to 5750 Å	5400	(i) Doja <i>et al.</i> , this <i>Journal</i> 1942, 19, 377. (ii) Doja and Prasad, <i>loc. cit.</i>
2- <i>p</i> -Dimethylamino-styryl- β -naphthoquinoline ethiodide	480	Lustrous needles	228-235°	5250	3600 to 7000 Å	6200	(i) Mills and Raper, <i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1925, 3473 (ii) Bloch and Hamer, <i>Phot. J.</i> , 1930, 70, 374.
2- <i>p</i> -Dimethylamino-styrylquinoline ethiodide	430	Prisms	249°	5300	3600 to 6750 Å	4700	(i) König and Treichel, <i>J. prakt. Chem.</i> , 1921, 102, 63. (ii) Bloch and Hamer, <i>loc. cit.</i>
2- <i>p</i> -Diethylamino-styrylpyridine ethiodide	380	Reddish violet plates	265°	4700	3600 to 6500 Å	5400	(i) Doja <i>et al.</i> , this <i>Journal</i> , 1942, 19, 125. (ii) Bloch and Hamer, <i>loc. cit.</i>

Here only among the β -naphthyl compounds is the diethyl derivative clearly superior to the dimethyl one. In the other cases it is not so true. The comparison of the melting points of these compounds is also not without interest. It increases with

decreasing molecular weight. Not quite the expected thing. In the bottom set it is consistently so; in the top set the pyridine compound only is an exception, having an m. p. lower than the corresponding quinoline compound. It is also noteworthy that in every case the dimethylamino compound has a lower m. p. than the corresponding diethylamino compound, notwithstanding the heavier molecular weight of the former (cf. Doja and Banerjee, this *Journal*, 1946, 28, 222).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

β -Naphthaquinaldine Ethiodide.— β -Naphthaquinaldine (1.0 g.) and ethyl iodide (0.8 g.) were heated together in a sealed tube on a water-bath for 26 hours. The yellow substance thus produced was crystallised from water and then recrystallised from alcohol, yield 1.10 g. (60.84%), m. p. 235-36°. (Found: I, 36.27. $C_{18}H_{18}NI$ requires I, 36.38 per cent).

2-Diethylaminostyryl- β -naphthaquinoline Ethiodide.— β -Naphthaquinaldine ethiodide (0.50 g.), *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.25 g.) and piperidine (4 drops) were shaken up in a flask with 10 c. c. of alcohol. A red colour developed in the cold, which deepened on warming. The solution was refluxed for 4 hours and the dye preprecipitated out with ether. It was recrystallised from methyl alcohol, yield, 0.53 g. (72.8%), m. p. 139°. (Found: N, 5.74; I, 24.91. $C_{27}H_{29}N_2I$ requires N, 5.71; I, 25.0 per cent).

1:1'-Diethyl-2':6'-dimethyl- β -naphthaisocyanine Iodide.— β -Naphthaquinaldine ethiodide (0.80 g.) and *p*-toluquinaldine ethiodide (0.74 g.) were completely dissolved in 15 c. c. of alcohol. To this was added all at once a solution of 0.1 g. of caustic potash in the smallest necessary quantity of alcohol. The colour changed from yellow to dark brown and then to deep reddish violet. The solution was refluxed for 6 hours and then left overnight at the room temperature. A few needle clusters appeared at the bottom of the flask. It was further cooled in a frigidaire for 24 hours, and the separated crystals recrystallised from ethyl alcohol, yield 0.345 g. (28.28%), m. p. 225°. (Found: N, 5.22; I, 23.85. $C_{20}H_{20}N_2I$ requires N, 5.26; I, 23.87 per cent).

1:1'-Diethyl-2'-methyl-6'-ethoxyl- β -naphthaisocyanine Iodide.—In a hot solution of β -naphthaquinaldine ethiodide (0.8 g.), 6'-ethoxyquinaldine ethiodide (0.8 g.) and alcohol (16 c. c.), was poured a strong alcoholic solution of caustic potash (0.1 g.), when the colour changed to strong violet. The contents of the flask were heated on a water-bath for 8 hours and then left to stand for 3 days. Tiny needles separated out which were carefully washed and recrystallised from ethyl alcohol, yield 0.310 g. (24.06%), m. p. 220°. (Found: N, 5.18; I, 22.55. $C_{30}H_{31}N_2I$ requires N, 4.98; I, 22.59 per cent).

1:1'-Diethyl-6'-methyl- β -naphthaisocyanine Iodide.— β -Naphthaquinaldine ethiodide (0.8 g.) and *p*-toluquinoline ethiodide (0.68 g.) were dissolved in hot alcohol (15 c. c.) to which a solution of caustic potash (0.1 g.) in a very small quantity of alcohol was added. The red solution was gently boiled for 6 hours and then slowly cooled for 24 hours. Some crystals appeared which increased on standing for another 24 hours.

These were recrystallised from ethyl alcohol, yield 0.520 g. (43.80%), m. p. 218° (Found : N, 5.36 ; I, 24.48. $C_{22}H_{27}N_2I$ requires N, 5.40 ; I, 24.51 per cent).

The yield and melting points given above are all those of twice recrystallised specimens.

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